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Electronic Banking and Students' Payment Performance in Alvan Ikoku Federal University of Education, Owerri, Imo-State

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ABSTRACT

This research analyzed electronic banking and students' payment performance in Alvan Ikoku Federal University of Education, Owerri. The specific objective of the study was to determine the relationship between transactions made via mobile pay and to ascertain the students' payment performance of banks in Alvan Ikoku Federal University of Education, Owerri. The data on electronic banking transactions were sourced from the Central Bank of Nigeria Statistical Bulletin while the data on students' payment performance was sourced from the volume of processed transactions of selected banks. A simple linear regression model was estimated. The results revealed that there is no significant effect of mobile pay banking services on the student's payment performance whereas there is significant effect of e-banking and students payment performance. The conclusion from the findings was that electronic banking services have increasingly enhanced the performance of banks in Nigeria most especially mobile banking channels. Students' payment performance rate of banks significantly suggests that banks have been making significant progress in their profitability ratio given increased access to electronic banking channels. It was recommended among others that, electronic banking channels should be more secured, efficient, strictly monitored, provided with adequate infrastructure and increased access to mobile phone services in order to return adequate profits to banks through the use of e-banking channels.

Keywords: Electronic Banking, Mobile Banking Services and Students' Payment Performance Rate.

INTRODUCTION

Electronic banking (e-banking) enables remote processing of financial inquiries and transactions without physical branch visits (Fozia, 2018). In Nigeria, traditional cash/cheque-based banking (pre-1980s)

evolved into e-banking following reforms addressing operational inefficiencies (Oluwatosin, 2017). The innovations and inventions in the field of Information and Communication Technologies (ICTs) facilitated the emergence of electronic banking popularly known as e-banking in the 1980s. The Automated Teller Machine (ATM) was conventionally introduced as an electronic delivery channel in 1989, and was first installed by National Cash Registers (NCR) for the defunct *Societe Generale* Bank of Nigeria (SGBN) in the same year.

Nigeria fully adopted electronic banking system in the early 2000s (CBN, 2019). Prior to 2003, a small number of banks operated their own propriety ATM fleets (Oluwatosin, 2017). The National Cash Registers (NCS) installed the very first ATM for the defunct *Societe Generale* Bank back in 1987 and the ATM commenced restricted use in 1989. Fast forward to the early 2000s, developments at home, such as the introduction of mobile telephone in 2001 and improved access to personal computers and Internet service facilities added to the growth of electronic banking in the country. The main shared ATM network in Nigeria, Inter-switch, began operations in 2003 with 5 ATMs from United Bank for Africa (UBA) and First Bank of Nigeria (Onodugo & Ifeanyi, 2015). However, since 2009 when e-banking services became fully open to the public, ATM transactions have averaged N2.5 trillion for the period 2009 to 2021 while mobile pay services averaged N422 billion within the same period (NIBSS, 2021). There is rapid adoption of other electronic payment services most especially the point-of-service (POS) and most recently, the block chain technology. These developments raise critical questions regarding the extent to which electronic banking influences payment performance, especially within educational institutions.

Electronic banking enables students and parents to pay fees instantly. Through mobile banking apps, internet transfers, POS terminals, and USSD codes, transactions that previously took days via cash deposits can now be completed in minutes. This reduces payment delays that often lead to administrative bottlenecks (e.g., late registration, withheld exam access). Furthermore, Payment compliance and convenience are increased as electronic banking reduces the burden of physically visiting bank branches or school cash offices (Nwosu et al .,2015). Most institutions have integrated payment portals with automated receipts and real-time confirmation. This convenience encourages more students to pay on time which improves revenue flows for the institution.

The main motivation for this study was examine the relationship between these electronic banking statistics and student's payment performance in the education sector in Nigeria with focus on Alvan Ikoku Federal University of Education, Owerri. Specifically, the study sought to determine the relationship between mobile banking and Student's Payment performance of banks and to ascertain the relationship between Student's Payment performance of banks in Alvan Ikoku Federal University of Education, Owerri.

Literature Review

Theoretical Framework

1. Theory of Financial Inclusion

The International Monetary Fund (IMF) theorized in the early 2000s that financial intermediation has advanced to the level of reaching the rural unbanked and making banking services to be universal which can equally help to advance the objective of banking which is to increase profitability and at the same time enhancing access to financial services. The International Monetary Fund (IMF) hypothesized that there is need to make financial services to reach the unreached and the unbanked. The importance of financial inclusion for long-term growth has further pushed the agenda of financial inclusion forward (Amidžić, Massara & Mialou, 2014).

The theoretical position of the IMF is that financial services should be promoted at the rural level through the offering of electronic banking services through agent banking. This, according to the agency will make the unbanked to be on a decreasing trend in most rural communities. The promotion of financial inclusion through its engagement with financial institutions and intermediaries will aid financial intermediation. The Financial inclusion theory stresses the access by enterprises and households to reasonably priced and appropriate formal financial services that meet the needs of enterprises and

households (World Bank, 2000). Financial inclusion means that individuals and businesses have access to useful and affordable financial products and services that meet their needs, transactions, payments, savings credits and insurance- delivered in a responsible and sustainable way (World Bank, 2000). It follows that persons that do not have access to banking services are regarded as financially excluded. This brings us to the concept of financial exclusion. The World Bank identified two types of financial exclusion namely: voluntary (or self-exclusion) and involuntary exclusion

Voluntary exclusion refers to people who do not identify their need for financial services or choose to remain outside of the financial system due to cultural or religious considerations. Involuntary exclusion refers to exclusion due to insufficient income, discrimination, lack of information, price barriers etc. (World Bank, 2014). In developing countries, the security concern of ordinary people carrying cash has become an additional motivation to address financial exclusion of the vast unbanked sector. Globally, the World Bank estimates that two billion people, of whom more than half are adults, do not have a bank account. In Africa, only one in four persons has a bank account, but eight in ten have access to a mobile phone.

Empirical studies found that emphasis on the financial inclusion hypothesis can alleviate poverty, reduce income inequality and increase the wealth of the low-income population (Levine, 1998; Demirgüç-Kunt & Klapper, 2012; Honohan, 2008). The growing evidence of the benefits to individuals of financial inclusion, especially having a bank account provides an economic and political rationale for governments and policy makers to promote financial inclusion (Klapper & Singer, 2015; Allen, 2016). Swamy (2014) stated that access to safe, easy, and affordable credit and other financial services by the poor and vulnerable groups, disadvantaged areas and lagging sectors is recognized as a pre-condition for accelerating growth and reducing income disparities and poverty.

Despite the growing evidence on the benefits of financial inclusion, differences remain on the optimal policies to promote both financial and economic development. On the practical side there is mounting global interest by donors, governments, regulators, banking and the commercial sectors in the use of mobile technologies to deliver financial services to emerging economies.

Porteous (2006) pointed out that there are four main categories of electronic banking business models:

- Bank-led,
- Telecom-led,
- Independent non-telecom and
- Non-bank agents, and any combination or hybrid of bank and non-bank partnerships.

The type of business model employed is determined mainly by the regulatory framework in that country. In Nigeria, the practice is the hybrid model. Bank and non-bank led model of mobile money services is typically regulated by strict banking regulations in addition to regulation by the telecoms regulators. The regulation is normally driven by the government's definition of e-money and therefore the regulation of mobile money. Mobile network operators provide the network infrastructure required for mobile payments, thus providing convenience to customers and ease of use. Mobile banking is able to leverage off the existing mobile telecommunication networks to provide financial services to the previously unbanked. Financial institutions have also launched their own mobile applications by entering into partnerships with the mobile networks to provide financial services. Electronic banking is able to overcome the high costs associated with fixed line telecommunication networks, as there are lower costs for building infrastructure, and lower costs associated with the development, provision and use of the services.

Therefore, this theory is upholding the fact that banks are pioneering the use of mobile and technological innovations to address financial inclusion (Alliance for Financial Inclusion 2011). Accordingly, the profit accruable to banks should be on the positive trend with the increase in electronic banking channels and the addition of more people into the banking system. Banks now have access to investible funds. These funds are invested and Return On Investments are earned. The Central Bank of Nigeria recently released bank profitability statement and the statistics show that the financial inclusion theory strongly holds good fortunes for the banking sub-sector in Nigeria.

2 Theory of Technology Acceptance Model (TAM)

The theory of Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) was postulated by Fred Davis (1989) and is specifically tailored towards modeling users' acceptance of information systems or technologies. The theory states that users of technology come to accept and use a new technology. By undergoing three stages whereby external factors trigger cognitive responses which in turn form an affective response which makes them to make use of the technology. The introduction of Information Communication Technology (ICT) changed the way individuals and organizations carry out different activities. It has allowed customers to access and perform several financial and banking transactions on their individual bank accounts from their computer at any time. Technological innovations no doubt, pose several challenges to institutions and organizations ranging from the user's willingness to accept, use available system and the pressing need to meet up with the trend of customer service delivery

Davis (1989), in a study, perceived usefulness, perceived ease of use and user acceptance of information technology, utilize the definitions of these variables to regress for reliability and construct validity in two studies involving a total of 152 users and four application programs. In both studies, usefulness had a significantly greater correlation with usage behavior than did ease of use. The result of the regression analysis suggests that perceived ease of use may actually be a causal antecedent to perceived usefulness, as opposed to a parallel direct determinant of system usage. Obviously, this theory came into existence after the financial intermediation theory (1960). However, the modifications of the financial intermediation theory by Andriein 2009, other aspects of the theory were studied including the role of technology in advancing financial intermediation, thus, the relevance of the TAM model.

Robey in Davis (1989), agreed that a system that does not help people perform their job is not likely to be received favorably. The model suggests that when users are presented with a new technology, a number of factors influence their decision about how and when they will use it.

- **Perceived usefulness (PU):** This according to Fred Davis is, "the degree to which a person believes that using a particular system will enhance his or her job performance". It refers to the perception of whether or not a technology will be useful for what someone wants to do.
- **Perceived Ease of Use (PEOU):** This was defined as "the degree to which a person believes that using a particular system would be free from effort", (Davis, 1989). This therefore means that if the technology is easy to use, then the barrier is conquered, but where it is not easy to be used and the inter-phase is complicated, no one has a positive attitude towards it.

Other external variables such as social influence were also identified as an important factor to determine the attitude. People's attitude influence intention to use a technology. Perception may also differ depending on age and gender.

Fig. 1: Technology Acceptance Model (TAM)

Source: Davis, 1989

TAM has been utilized by many researchers to understand the acceptance of different types of information systems as they aid service delivery. The TAM model has been modified to include more variables that made it more robust. It has therefore been useful especially in the understanding of a user behavior of information technology systems.

In the context of this study, both the banking sub-sector and the customers are the users of electronic banking channels (technology). This means that the level of acceptance of the technology depends on the effectiveness of its deployment by banks. Thus, the acceptance of any electronic banking service is predicted by the users' behavior intention, which is in turn, determined by the perception of technology usefulness in performing the task. There are two scenarios in this case. Firstly, the perceived usefulness of the e-banking channel is what will inform the attitude and behavioral pattern of the customers. Secondly, the banks perceived the ease of use of the e-banking channels as a way of growing their profits.

This research is therefore hinged on the financial inclusion theory and the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM). As earlier explained, TAM is an information systems theory that models how people come to accept a new policy and use technology that has the potential of enhancing the performance of banks. TAM is one of the models that have been developed to provide a better understanding of the usage and adoption of technology which is the base of electronic banking. It is presently a prominent theory used in modeling technology acceptance and adoption in information systems research.

The model suggests that when people or institutions are presented with a new technology, a number of factors influence their decision about how and when they will use it. The factors are; perceived usefulness (PU) and perceived ease-of-use (PEOU). According to TAM, one's actual use of a technology system is influenced directly or indirectly by the user's behavioral intentions, attitude, perceived usefulness of the system, and perceived ease of the system. Similarly, the financial inclusion theory upholds the universality of banks and the spread of banking services to the rural areas. Embedding technology in banking helps to drive this objective and the ease of acceptance of technology by both the banks and the customers makes financial inclusion seamless and easy for banks. It follows that when banking services are well spread and well accepted because of its perceived benefits, the performance of banks will be enhanced in the long run.

Empirical Framework

A number of studies have examined the linkage between electronic banking channels and banks' performance both in Nigeria and outside Nigerian economy. One common feature of the previous studies is their consistent use of any of the e-banking channels such as mobile, POS, ATM or internet banking services. However, our review shall disaggregate the empirical works carried out on Mobile Pay as it affects the student's payment performance of banks in Alvan Ikoku Federal University of Education, Owerri..

Jannang and Abdullah (2016) conducted a study on "effect of mobile pay banking service quality and accessibility on students' loyalty through customer satisfaction using Generalized Structured Component Analysis (GSCA) and found that mobile pay banking service quality and accessibility has a significant effect on customer loyalty through student's satisfaction. Fozia, (2018) conducted an empirical study on impact of mobile banking on overall students satisfaction in India using regression analysis found that dimensions of mobile pay banking, i.e, security and privacy in public banks, accessibility and ease of use variables have significant impact on overall customer satisfaction.

Chukwukaelo, Onyeiwe and Amah (2018) employed a panel data regression to estimate the relationship between mobile pay banking and the profitability of organizations in Nigeria. They collected data on mobile pay banking from 10 banks operating in the country and regressed the mobile pay banking transaction costs on the return on equity of the banks. Findings from the study showed that mobile pay banking and profitability of deposit money banks had a significant positive relationship establishment in Nigeria.

Farouk and Saheed (2018) focused their study on tertiary institutions in Kaduna State by investigating the impact of mobile pay banking on students' satisfaction with the application of both quantitative and

qualitative methods. It was discovered from the research that mobile pay banking services and electronic banking products have a significant positive impact on the satisfaction of the students of tertiary institutions banks in Kaduna State, Nigeria.

Khazaei (2018) conducted empirical research on the effect of mobile banking service convenience on students satisfaction and behavioral responses in the banking industry using structural equation model (SEM). The study found out that mobile pay banking service convenience has a positive effect on students' satisfaction and behavioural responses. Babatunde and Salawudeen (2017) assessed the impact of electronic banking on financial institutions and banking industry in Nigeria with the employment of both descriptive and inferential statistics in analyzing the data. They focused mainly on banking made over the web. They used data on returns on assets to represent bank efficiency, regulatory quality to represent bank effectiveness and total deposit liability to represent bank productivity while also adding e-banking penetration rate as intervening variable. Total bank density was their dependent variable. The study concluded that electronic banking emergence facilitated the efficiency, effectiveness and productivity of the banks in Nigeria.

Sadaf & Rahela (2017) employed judgmental and convenience sampling of 194 internet banking customers to examine the relationship between various dimensions of internet banking service quality and satisfaction of customers in India. They concluded from the study that internet service quality dimensions have a significant impact on the customer satisfaction in the country. Iluno & Yakubu (2017) utilized both descriptive and regression analysis to examine the connection between electronic commerce and customer satisfaction in Kaduna State Polytechnic. The authors posited that internet reliability, inefficiency and security in the selected banks brought about a significant impact on customers' satisfaction. Sui & Mon (2018) examined the perception of customers regarding the service quality dimension and impact of e-service quality dimensions on customer satisfaction in internet banking. Factors like credibility, efficiency, problem handling and security were used to find the perception of customers towards the service quality dimensions in internet banking. The data from 195 customers of banks were selected using an e-SERVIQUAL questionnaire and tools like factor analysis; t-test, one-way ANOVA and multiple regression tests were used to find the perception of customers. Finding suggests that all three dimensions such as credibility, efficiency, problem handling, were found to be important in determining the overall service quality perceptions of customers except security. From the regression test, findings reveal the credibility, problem handling and security have significant impact on customer satisfaction.

Ashiru, Balogun & Paseda (2023) investigated the impact of internet banking on banks' financial performance. Schumpeter's Theory of Innovation Diffusion and constraint-induced financial innovation theories were the theoretical foundation of the study. Utilizing data for the 2012 to 2021 period because of data availability, they considered the causal effect of innovation on commercial bank performance via Granger causality test. The entire 24 deposit money banks in Nigeria constituted the study's population. Secondary data were gathered over the study period from NDIC annual reports, the Nigeria Inter-Bank Settlement System (NIBSS), and the Central Bank of Nigeria statistical bulletins (2012–2021). Based on the ARDL model analysis, POS banking service had the greatest impact on deposit money bank performance because of large volume and value of transaction witnessed in the banking sector. Thus, they suggested that more mobile and e-banking services should be made available. The usage of ATMs, mobile banking, credit and debit cards, online banking, and agency banking had positive short run and long run substantial effect on deposit money bank performance in Nigeria, except National Electronic Fund Transfer (NEFT) and NIBSS Instant Payments (NIP) according to empirical results.

METHOD

Research Design

This research adopted the *ex-post-facto* research design. The researchers opted for this design approach because we intended to use secondary data to achieve our specific objectives. The *ex-post-facto* design is a quasi-experimental study which examines how an independent variable affects a dependent variable. A quasi-experimental study simply means that the variables studied are not randomly assigned and that the

observations have been made and kept for reference and inferential purposes. For this study, the design involved gathering of time series data that have cross-sectional properties i.e. data from five different banks and students' payment performance, subjecting the time series data to econometric analysis of unit root, cointegration and panel model estimation.

Instruments for Data Collection

Secondary data were used in this study. They were sourced mostly from the publications of the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) Statistical Bulletin, vol. 32, 2021, National Bureau of Statistics and the Nigeria Inter-Bank Settlement System (NIBSS) 2021 publications. The variables for which data were sourced include: values of Mobile, ATM, POS and Web/internet banking transactions, returns on assets and students payment performance rate for the period between 2009 through 2021. The econometric software packages used for the analysis was the E-Views version10 software.

Test of Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance. The decision rule is that, if the resulting probability value is small (less than 0.05) the critical value, we reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternate hypothesis. If the probability value is equal to or greater than the critical value (0.05), we accept the null hypothesis and reject the alternate hypothesis.

H₀₁: There is no significant effect of Mobile Pay Banking Services on the students' payment performance of banks in Alvan Ikoku Federal University of Education, Owerri.

H₀₂: There is no significant effect of students' payment performance on banks' in Alvan Ikoku Federal University of Education, Owerri.

The hypotheses were tested based on the t-statistic values and their respective probability values. The overall significance of the individual variables was also tested using the F-statistic in order to give a general report of the test of hypotheses. The t-test is summarized as follows:

Table : Test of Hypotheses

Hypotheses I	Variables	t-stat.	p-value	Decision
H ₀₁ : There is no significant effect of mobile pay banking services on the students payment performance of the banks in Alvan Ikoku Federal University Of Education, Owerri.	MOB	0.44207	0.6600 > 0.05	The <i>p-value</i> is not significant therefore, we accept the null hypothesis and conclude that there is no significant effect of mobile banking on the students payment performance in Alvan Ikoku Federal University of Education, Owerri.
Hypotheses II	Variables	t-stat.	p-value	Decision
H ₀₂ : There is no significant effect of e-banking on students payment performance rate of banks' in Alvan Ikoku Federal University of Education, Owerri.	EBP	4.1993	0.0001 < 0.05	The <i>p-value</i> is significant therefore; we reject the null hypothesis and conclude that there is significant effect of e-banking on students payment performance rate of banks' in Alvan Ikoku Federal University of Education, Owerri.

Source: Extracted from E-views Output

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

In this sub-section, the results from the analysis made in chapter four are collated in order to give a comprehensive view of the significance and direction of the study. The aim of this is to draw conclusions and make comparisons with the previous literature that will establish the area best suited for policy implementation in order to enhance the performance of banks vis-à-vis electronic banking transactions. The test shows that for hypothesis one, we accept the null hypothesis since the probability value of 0.6600 is greater than the 0.05 critical value and as such, we conclude that there is no significant effect of mobile pay banking services on the students payment performance of banks in Alvan Ikoku Federal University of Education, Owerri. The hypothesis two has probability value of 0.0001, which is less than 0.05 critical value. Therefore, we conclude that there is significant effect of e-banking and students payment performance rate on banks' in Alvan Ikoku Federal University of Education, Owerri.

Conclusion

E-banking channels significantly improve banks' ROA through efficient student payment processing at Alvan Ikoku University. Mobile banking alone requires strategic enhancement to realize its potential. The importance of electronic banking in enhancing the students' payment performance rate of banks in Alvan Ikoku Federal University of Education, Owerri cannot be over-emphasized. Deposit Money Banks have no doubt benefitted from innovative banking services such as mobile, internet and even point-of-sale banking services. This study did a thorough analysis of electronic banking channels and their effect on the ROA of banks in Nigeria and made some useful findings. The conclusion from the findings is that electronic banking services have increasingly enhanced students' payment performance of selected banks in Alvan Ikoku Federal University of Education, Owerri most especially mobile and ATM banking channels. The ratio of electronic banking transactions to GDP (students payment performance rate) increasingly enhanced ROA of banks significantly which suggests that banks have been making significant progress in their profitability ratio given increased access to electronic banking channels.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings, the study recommends as follows:

1. There is need to enhance mobile banking security, infrastructure, and rural access to strengthen its impact.
2. The CBN should promote e-banking adoption through customer education and channel diversification.
3. Banks should optimize multi-channel (ATM/POS/web) integration for student transactions.

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